

Heterocycles from Sulphamylphenylhydrazines. Part I. 2-(*p*-Sulphamylphenyl)-1,2,3-benzotriazoles and their 1-Oxides

Anil Prakash and I. R. Gambhir

2-(*p*-Sulphamylphenyl)-1,2,3-benzotriazoles and their 1-oxides have been obtained by condensation of halogeno-nitrobenzenes and *p*-sulphamylphenylhydrazine and characterised. The hydrazo compound is first formed which cyclises to a benzotriazole 1-oxide in acetic acid medium and to benzotriazole in ethanolic medium. The former can be reduced to the latter by treatment with ethanol.

p-Sulphamylphenylhydrazine reacts with halogenated nitrobenzenes, having a nitro group in their *ortho* position, to form hydrazo compounds by replacement of the hydrogen of hydrazino group with halogen atom; the hydrogens of the sulphamyl group remain unaffected. Thus when *p*-sulphamylphenylhydrazine was treated with 1-chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene in ethanolic solution at ordinary temperature and in presence of sodium acetate, 2,4-dinitro-4'-sulphamylhydrazobenzene (I) was formed; in acetic acid solution, however, only acetyl derivative of *p*-sulphamylphenylhydrazine (Ac. NH. NH. C₆H₄SO₂.NH₂) was isolated. Compound (I), when heated in acetic acid solution, furnished 6-nitro-2-(*p*-sulphamylphenyl)-1,2,3-benzotriazole-1-oxide (II), whereas heating in ethanolic solution for about 3 hours yielded 6-nitro-2-(*p*-sulphamylphenyl)-1,2,3-benzotriazole (III). Compound (II) on heating in ethanolic solution is reduced to provide compound (III). The structure of these benzotriazoles and their 1-oxides follows from the analogous derivatives of phenylhydrazines¹⁻⁵. Further, the acetyl derivative (IV) of compound (II) (also formed by heating compound I with acetic anhydride), when boiled with ethanol for a few hours, yielded compound (V), which was identical with the one obtained from compound (III) and acetic anhydride.

The behaviour of other halogenated nitrobenzenes, such as 1-chloro-2,6-dinitro-, 1,2-dichloro-4,6-dinitro-, 1,3-dichloro-4,6-dinitro-, 1,4-dichloro-2,6-dinitro-, 1-chloro-2,6-dinitro-4-methyl-, 1-chloro-4,6-dinitro-3-methyl-, 1-chloro-2,4,6-trinitro-3-methyl-, 1-chloro-2-bromo-4,6-dinitro- and 1-chloro-4-bromo-2,6-dinitro-benzene, was also identical. These too formed the corresponding hydrazo compounds, triazoles, and their 1-oxides. 1-Chloro-2,4,6-trinitrobenzene, however, when treated with *p*-sulphamylphenylhydrazine in acetic acid solution, furnished the hydrazo derivative; no acetyl derivative of the hydrazine in this case was isolated.

1. Wittig, *Ber.*, 1912, 45, 2381.

2. Gandmougin, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1907, ii, 76, 134; *Ber.*, 1903, 36, 3822.

3. Willgerodt and Ferko, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1888, ii, 37, 351; *Ber.*, 1891, 24, 1661.

4. Gius, *Gazzetta*, 1918, 48, 11, 13.

5. Sane and Joshi, *this Journal*, 1953, 10, 459.

EXPERIMENTAL

2,4-Dinitro-4'-sulphamylhydrazobenzene (I).— 1-Chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene (2.0 g.), *p*-sulphamylphenylhydrazine (1.9 g.), and sodium acetate (1.0 g.) in ethanol (15 ml) were heated on a water bath for $\frac{1}{4}$ hr. The solid separating on cooling was recrystallised from ethanol and provided 60% of the product as golden yellow flakes, m.p. 208°. (Found: S, 9.00. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_6\text{N}_3\text{S}$ requires S, 9.06%).

By adopting a similar procedure, a few sulphamylhydrazobenzenes have been prepared and are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Sulphamylhydrazobenzenes.

No.	Halogeno-nitrobenzene.	Yield.	M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
					Found.	Reqd.
1	1-Chloro-2,6-dinitro-	56 %	209°	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_6\text{N}_3\text{S}$	9.00	9.06
2	1-Chloro-2,4,6-trinitro-	62	221°	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_8\text{N}_6\text{S}$	7.97	8.04
3	1,2-Dichloro-4,6-dinitro-	60	210°	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_6\text{N}_3\text{Cl}_2\text{S}$	8.21	8.26
4	1,3-Dichloro-4,6-dinitro-	64	206°	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_6\text{N}_3\text{Cl}_2\text{S}$	8.21	8.26
5	1,4-Dichloro-2,6-dinitro-	61	269°	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_6\text{N}_3\text{Cl}_2\text{S}$	8.19	8.26
6	1-Chloro-2,6-dinitro-4-methyl-	61	210°	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_6\text{N}_3\text{S}$	8.64	8.72
7	1-Chloro-4,6-dinitro-3-methyl-	58	205°	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_6\text{N}_3\text{S}$	8.65	8.72
8	1-Chloro-2,4,6-trinitro-3-methyl-	60	220°	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_8\text{N}_6\text{S}$	7.71	7.77
9	1-Chloro-2-bromo-4,6-dinitro-	52	197°	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_6\text{N}_3\text{BrS}$	7.32	7.41
10	1-Chloro-4-bromo-2,6-dinitro-	52	204°	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_6\text{N}_3\text{BrS}$	7.30	7.41

6-Nitro-2-(*p*-sulphamylphenyl)-1,2,3-benzotriazole-1-oxide (II).—A solution of compound (I) (2.0 g.) in acetic acid (10 ml) was refluxed for 3 hr. The precipitate separating on cooling was recrystallised from EtOH-AcOH (1:1), furnishing 55% of the product (II) as yellow needles, m.p. 225°. (Found: S, 9.51. $C_{12}H_9O_3N_3S$ requires S, 9.55%).

By adopting a similar procedure a few *p*-sulphamylphenyl-1,2,3-benzotriazole-1-oxides have been prepared and are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

2-*p*-Sulphamylphenyl-1,2,3-benzotriazole-1-oxides.

*No.	2- <i>p</i> -Sulphamylphenyl-benzotriazole-1-oxide.	Yield.	M.P.	Formula.	%Sulphur.		Acetyl derivative m.p.
					Found.	Reqd.	
1	4-Nitro-	55 %	229°	$C_{12}H_9O_3N_3S$	9.50	9.55	153°
2	4,6-Dinitro.	55	241°	$C_{12}H_7O_7N_6S$	8.36	8.42	150°
3	4-Chloro-6-nitro.	52	216°	$C_{12}H_8O_2N_3ClS$	8.61	8.66	139°
4	5-Chloro-6-nitro.	52	219°	$C_{12}H_8O_2N_3ClS$	8.60	8.66	146°
5	6-Chloro-4-nitro.	52	281°	$C_{12}H_8O_2N_3ClS$	8.60	8.66	170°
6	4-Nitro-6-methyl.	51	217°	$C_{13}H_{11}O_3N_3S$	9.10	9.17	147°
7	6-Nitro-5-methyl.	51	213°	$C_{13}H_{11}O_3N_3S$	9.09	9.17	142°
8	4,6-Dinitro-7-methyl.	53	226°	$C_{13}H_{10}O_7N_6S$	8.04	8.12	152°
9	4-Bromo-6-nitro.	50	206°	$C_{12}H_8O_3N_3BrS$	7.67	7.73	139°
10	6-Bromo-4-nitro.	50	215°	$C_{12}H_8O_3N_3BrS$	7.64	7.73	147°

*As recorded in Table I.

6-Nitro-2-(*p*-sulphamylphenyl)-1,2,3-benzotriazole (III)

Method A.—A solution of compound (I) (2.0 g.) in ethanol (15 ml) was refluxed for 4 hr. On cooling a precipitate separated. Recrystallisation from ethanol provided 64% of the product (III) as golden yellow needles, m.p. 231°. (Found: S, 9.94. $C_{12}H_9O_4N_3S$ requires S, 10.03%).

TABLE III

2-*p*-Sulphamylphenyl-1,2,3-benzotriazoles.

*No.	2- <i>p</i> -Sulphamylphenyl-benzotriazole.	Yield.	M.P.	Formula.	%Sulphur.		Acetyl derivative m.p.
					Found.	Reqd.	
1.	4-Nitro-	64 %	247°	$C_{12}H_9O_4N_3S$	9.97	10.03	275°
2.	4,6-Dinitro.	64	251°	$C_{12}H_7O_8N_6S$	8.74	8.79	280°
3.	4-Chloro-6-nitro.	61	222°	$C_{12}H_8O_4N_3ClS$	9.26	9.31	260°
4.	5-Chloro-6-nitro.	61	228°	$C_{12}H_8O_4N_3ClS$	9.26	9.31	252°
5.	6-Chloro-4-nitro.	60	305°	$C_{12}H_8O_4N_3ClS$	9.25	9.31	323°
6.	4-Nitro-6-methyl.	62	224°	$C_{13}H_{11}O_4N_3S$	9.53	9.61	257°
7.	6-Nitro-5-methyl.	62	222°	$C_{13}H_{11}O_4N_3S$	9.55	9.61	254°
8.	4,6-Dinitro-7-methyl.	64	232°	$C_{13}H_{10}O_8N_6S$	8.39	8.46	274°
9.	4-Bromo-6-nitro.	58	210°	$C_{12}H_8O_4N_3BrS$	7.97	8.04	231°
10.	6-Bromo-4-nitro.	58	220°	$C_{12}H_8O_4N_3BrS$	7.98	8.04	249°

*As recorded in Table I.

Method B.—Compound (II) (1.0 g.) in ethanol (10 ml) was refluxed for 3 hr. Recrystallisation from ethanol furnished 68% of compound (III).

Method C.—1-Chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene (1.0 g.), *p*-sulphamylphenylhydrazine (1.5 g.), and sodium acetate (0.5 g.) in ethanol (10 ml) were refluxed for 5 hr. The solid separating on cooling was recrystallised from acetic acid, furnishing 60% of compound (III).

The mixed m.p. of compound (III), obtained by methods A, B and C, remained undepressed. By a similar procedure as above, a few *p*-sulphamylphenyl-1,2,3-benzotriazoles were prepared. These are recorded in Table III.

6-Nitro-2-(*p*-sulphacetamylphenyl)-1,2,3-benzotriazole-1-oxide (IV). *Method A.*—A solution of compound (I) (2.0 g.) in acetic anhydride (10 ml) was refluxed for 3 hr. On cooling and dilution, a precipitate separated which on recrystallisation from acetic acid afforded 55% of the product (IV) as pale yellow needles, m.p. 150°. (Found: S, 8.42% C₁₄H₁₁O₆N₃S requires S, 8.49%.)

Method B.—Compound (II) (2.0 g.) in acetic anhydride (10 ml) was refluxed for 2 hr. Recrystallisation from ethanol yielded 80% of compound (IV). Its mixed m.p. with the one obtained by method A remained undepressed.

6-Nitro-2-(*p*-sulphacetamylphenyl)-1,2,3-benzotriazole (V). *Method A.*—A solution of compound (IV) (1.9 g.) in ethanol (10 ml) was refluxed for 3 hr. The product separating on cooling was recrystallised from ethanol, providing 50% of compound (V) as yellow needles, m.p. 270°. (Found: S, 8.80%. C₁₄H₁₁O₅N₃S requires S, 8.86%.)

Method B.—A solution of compound (III) (2.0 g.) in acetic anhydride (10 ml) was refluxed for 2 hr. Recrystallisation from ethanol furnished 59% of compound (V).

Grateful acknowledgements are due to the Ministry of Scientific Research and Cultural Affairs, Government of India, for the award of a research scholarship to one of the authors (A.P.).